

COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES ON THE STUDY OF ETHICS-SUFISM

Communication Science Study Program
Class E2, Odd Semester of 2022-2023

Teaching Lecturer
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Faculty of Da'wa and Communication
Sunan Ampel State Islamic University
Surabaya, Indonesia, December 2022

Collection of the Article Novelties on the Study of Ethics-Sufism

Communication Science Study Program

Class E2, Odd Semester of 2022-2023

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PREFACE

This novelties collection is an output that shines from article reviews on Ethics and Sufism published by scientific journals. This collection is the result of the "Ethics and Sufism" lecture at the Communication Science Study Program, Faculty of Da'wa and Communication, Sunan Ampel State Islamic University, Surabaya, Indonesia, on Odd Semester of 2022-2023. The reviewers are the students concerned in class E2.

The teaching lecturer guides the reviewers who are divided into 12 teams with different articles. Each team reviewed one article. The review includes the description of the article that was reviewed, the description of previous researches, the discussion of the review, the preparation of novelty from the article abstract, and the contribution of article to the development of science insights, especially the study programs concerned.

The presence of this collection marked the progress of student's study since they were in the first semester in their S1 study range. This is a valuable achievement savings for them and can be an important rising ladder in their intellectual progress during the study period and at the next level of study.

On the end, the teaching lecturer conveyed congratulations and high appreciation to all students who contributed to this collection. Hopefully they can all achieve the best achievements in their studies with great useful knowledge for religion and people at large. *Amin.*

Surabaya, January 9, 2023

Lecturer & Reviewers

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COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023

- Review Number : #1-E2-22
- Article Title : Wajah Baru Urban Sufisme: Geliat Tasawuf Milenial Mahasiswa Ahlith Thariqah al-Mu'tabarah an-Nahdliyyah
- Author(s) : Muhammad Nabil Fahmi, Eva Latipah, dan Ismatul Izzah
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 8, no. 1 (June 17, 2022): 1–22.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/13622>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Urban sufisme merupakan sebuah fenomena sosial yang ditandai dengan meningkatnya gairah masyarakat terhadap praktik sufisme, seperti zikir berjamaah, *istighasah*, diskusi keislaman dan sebagainya.
- English Novelty : Urban Sufism is a social phenomenon marked by the increasing public passion for the practice of Sufism, such as dhikr in congregation, *istighasah*, discussions to Islam and so on.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Reviewer 2

Name : Achmad Adam Aminullah

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Name : Ahmad Fahimuddin Nur

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COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023

- Review Number : #2-E2-22
- Article Title : Pendidikan Tasawuf Ibnu Thufail dalam Novel Hayy bin Yaqdzan
- Author(s) : Husnul Qodim, Abdul Wasik, dan Fikri Taufiqur Rohman.
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 8, no. 1 (June 30, 2022): 103–128.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/8503>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Nilai-nilai pendidikan tasawuf Ibnu Thufail dalam novel Hayy bin Yaqdzan adalah *wara', zuhud, ridha, mahabbah, khauf, syauq, uns, thuma'ninah, yaqin, tauhid, mitsaq, dan fana'*
- English Novelty : The Sufism educational values of Ibn Thufail's within the novel Hayy bin Yaqdzan are devout, ascetism, willing, love, fear, longing, joy, tranquility, certainty, monotheism, existence, and courtyard

Reviewer Team

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Name : Alisia Rizki Sayyida

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COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023

- Review Number : #3-E2-22
- Article Title : Konstruksi Sabar al-Ghazali sebagai Terapi Sufistik dalam Meningkatkan Adversity Quotient Mahasiswa di Masa Pandemi Covid-19
- Author(s) : Achmad Shodiqil Hafil dan Ratnawati Ratnawati
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 8, no. 1 (June 17, 2022): 81–102.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/14259>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Terapi sabar ala sufi di masa pandemi Covid-19 menaikkan potensi Adversity Quotient mahasiswa setingkat Climbers, yakni manusia berjiwa optimis, tidak lemah oleh masalah, dan justru mengubah masalah menjadi tantangan.
- English Novelty : Sufi-style patient therapy during the Covid-19 pandemic increases the potential for Adversity Quotient students at the Climbers level, namely humans who are optimistic, not weak by problems, and instead turn problems into challenges.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

- Name : Alvida Meylia Aristanty
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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #4-E2-22
- Article Title : Doa dan Wirid al-A'la sebagai Metode Sufi Healing (Praktek Batatamba Guru Arni)
- Author(s) : Saniah Saniah
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 8, no. 1 (2022): 57–80.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/14145>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Proses penyembuhan penyakit, cara doa, dan wirid al-A'la merupakan salah satu alternatif dari metode penyembuhan yang lain. Doa dan wirid tersebut dilakukan oleh metode sufi healing yang digunakan oleh Guru Arni dan dapat digunakan untuk penyembuhan penyakit penyakit fisik, psikis, dan magis.
- English Novelty : The process of healing the disease, the way of prayer, and *wirid* al-A'la is one alternative to other healing methods. The prayer and *wirid* are carried out by the Sufi Healing method used by the teacher Arni and can be used to heal physical, psychological, and magical diseases.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

- Name : Dera Eka Candelia
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Reviewer 3

Name : Fadya Majida Az-Zahra
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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #5-E2-22
- Article Title : Tasawuf Education Concept in the Text of Sholawat Wahidiyah Based on al-Ghazali's Theory
- Author(s) : Husnul Khotimah
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 8, no. 1 (2022): 45–56.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/12269>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Pelaksanaan Shalawat Wahidiyah dari perspektif al-Ghazali menggunakan metode *mujahadah* dengan upaya yang sungguh-sungguh dalam pendekatan sufistik untuk memerangi hawa nafsu yang timbul dari dalam diri manusia serta meningkatkan daya *ma'rifat* terhadap Allah dan Rasulullah.
- English Novelty : The implementation of Shalawat Wahidiyah from the perspective of al-Ghazali uses the *mujahadah* (really effort) method with a serious effort in the Sufistic approach to fight the passions that arise from within humans and increase the power of *ma'rifat* (highest knowledge) towards Allah and the Prophet.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Fais Akbar
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Student ID Number : 04020522049

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Rusadi
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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #6-E2-22
- Article Title : Tarekat Alawiyah; Genealogi, Konsep Moderasi dan Peran Pembentukan NKRI
- Author(s) : Abdul Aziz Muslim dan Siti Zumrotus Sa'adah
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 8, no. 1 (2022): 23–44.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/13683>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Munculnya kelompok majelis zikir dan shalawat di setiap kota besar di Indonesia dengan konsep dakwah secara moderat yang mampu merangkul masyarakat luas.
- English Novelty : The emergence of the *dhikir* and *shalawat* Assembly Group in every major city in Indonesia with the concept of moderate da'wah that is able to embrace the wider community.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #7-E2-22
- Article Title : Pengalaman Spiritual dan Kebahagiaan Menurut Nyai Hajah Masriyah Amva
- Author(s) : Sulaiman Sulaiman
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 7, no. 2 (December 29, 2021): 211–230.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/13143>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Cara menurut Nyai Hj. Masriyah Amva untuk menciptakan kebahagiaan sampai akhir hayat melalui pengalaman spiritual. Dengan menjadikan Tuhan sebagai puncak tujuan dari transendensi diri, maka ia merasa Tuhan selalu dekat dengan-Nya sekaligus menjadi sandarannya di manapun, kapanpun, bahkan ketika ia sendirian.
- English Novelty : The way according to Nyai Hj. Masriyah Amva to create happiness until the end of life through spiritual experience. By making God the peak of the goal of self-transcendence, he feels that God is always close to Him at the same time being his back anywhere, anytime, even when he is alone.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Name : Ilham Akbar Nugraha

Student ID Number : 04020522056

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #8-E2-22
- Article Title : Being Tolerant and Nationalist Sufi: A Social Movement Study of JATMAN (Jam'iyyah Ahl al-Thariqot al-Mu'tabarah an-Nahdliyyah) and Habib Luthfi
- Author(s) : Achmad Jauhari Umar
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 7, no. 2 (December 16, 2021): 189–210.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/12746>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Logika gerakan sosial Jam'iyyah Ahl al-Thariqat al-Mu'tabarah an-Nahdliyyah (JATMAN) yang mengedepankan toleransi dan nasionalisme. Gerakan ini menyerukan 'bela negara' dengan jargon 'NKRI harga mati' (doktrin cinta tanah air) dan Handarbeni (bangga pada lokalitas).
- English Novelty : The social movement logic of the *Jam'iyyah Ahl al-Tariqat al-Mu'tabarah an-Nahdliyyah* (JATMAN) which prioritizes tolerance and nationalism. This movement calls for 'Defending the Country' with the jargon 'NKRI dead price' (doctrine of love of the motherland) and *handarbeni* (proud of locality).

Reviewer Team

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Reviewer 3

Name : Izzatunnisa' Azzahro

Student ID Number : 04020522059

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #9-E2-22
- Article Title : Fenomena Taubat pada Komunitas Forsabda di Tulungagung
- Author(s) : Mega Mustika Sari dan Achmad Sauqi
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 7, no. 2 (December 16, 2021): 171–188.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/11388>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Pemaknaan taubat pada pegiat Forsabda yakni kesadaran diri, evaluasi diri, ketauhidan, dan habluminallah. Sedangkan penerapan taubat pada pegiat forsabda ada *muhasabah*, tawakal, *tawadhu*, *istiqamah*, syukur, dan ketegangan batin.
- English Novelty : The meaning of repentance for Forsabda activists namely self-awareness, self-evaluation, monotheism, and relation to Allah. While the application of repentance to Forsabda activists is self-evaluation, trust, politeness, consistence, gratitude, and inner tension.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Reviewer 2

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Name : Lukman Aditya Maulana
Student ID Number : 04020522062

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #10-E2-22
- Article Title : Sufi Modernis: Peran Transformatif Mursyid TQN Suryalaya dalam Bidang Pendidikan, Ekonomi dan Lingkungan Hidup
- Author(s) : Asep Maulana Rohimat
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 7, no. 2 (December 16, 2021): 155–170.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/12747>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Peran mursyid TQN dalam transformasi kualitas masyarakat ke arah yang lebih baik dalam tiga bidang; (1) bidang pendidikan formal tingkat dasar, menengah, dan perguruan tinggi, (2) bidang ekonomi berupa kerjasama dengan UKM masyarakat sekitar, (3) bidang lingkungan hidup berupa konservasi alam, teknologi pengairan, dan perkebunan.
- English Novelty : The role of TQN Murshid in the transformation of the quality of society for the better in three fields; (1) formal education in elementary, secondary, and tertiary level, (2) economic in the form of cooperation with UKM surrounding communities, (3) environmental fields in the form of nature conservation, irrigation technology, and plantations.

Reviewer Team

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Name : Muhammad Faishal Haq

Student ID Number : 04020522065

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #11-E2-22
- Article Title : Konsep Amar Ma'ruf Nahi Munkar al-Ghazali dan Relevansinya dengan Nilai-Nilai Moderasi Beragama di Pondok Pesantren Sidogiri
- Author(s) : Zainul Mun'im
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 7, no. 2 (December 16, 2021): 135–154.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/8658>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Konsep dakwah kitab *Ihya'* dengan nilai-nilai moderasi beragama sangat berpengaruh terhadap paradigma berdakwah Pondok Pesantren Sidogiri yang moderat dan menggunakan pendekatan persuasif
- English Novelty : The preaching concept of the book of *Ihya'* with the values of religious moderation is very influential on the preaching paradigm of the Sidogiri Islamic Boarding School which is moderate and uses a persuasive approach.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Muhammad Fajar Eka
Febrianto

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Reviewer 2

Name : Muhammad Hisyam
Baihaqi

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Reviewer 3

Name : Muhammad Khoirul Huda

Student ID Number : 04020522068

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Ethics-Sufism, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #12-E2-22
- Article Title : “Pemberdayaan Pemuda Milenial Melalui Program Penguatan Jati Diri Insan Kamil di Komunitas Home Education Based Akhlak and Talent
- Author(s) : Suprima Suprima, Muhamad Parhan, Alma Shafira Reviana, Nurti Budiyanti, dan Agus Fakhruddin
- Publishing Information : Esoterik: Jurnal Akhlak dan Tasawuf 7, no. 2 (December 16, 2021): 115–134.
<https://journal.iainkudus.ac.id/index.php/esoterik/article/view/11289>
- Subject of the Study : Ethics-Sufism
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Communication Science, E2
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Penerapan model *fitrah assessment* dengan metode pendampingan agar pemuda memiliki paradigma berdaya dalam segi ekonomi, pengabdian kepada Allah, dan mampu memberi dampak pemberdayaan masyarakat yang terintegrasi antara mental dan spiritual, menularkan semangat ketauhidan, ilmu pengetahuan dan teknologi, serta adaptif terhadap perkembangan zaman.
- English Novelty : The application of the Fitrah Assessment model with the mentoring method so that youth have a paradigm of power in the economic aspects, devotion to God, and able to have an impact of integrated community empowerment between mental and spiritual, transmitting the spirit of devotion, science and technology, and adaptive to the time.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Reviewer 2

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This novelties collection is an output that shines from article reviews on Ethics and Sufism published by scientific journals. This collection is the result of the "Ethics and Sufism" lecture at the Communication Science Study Program, Faculty of Da'wa and Communication, Sunan Ampel State Islamic University, Surabaya, Indonesia, on Odd Semester of 2022-2023. The reviewers are the students concerned in class E2.

The presence of this collection marked the progress of student's study since they were in the first semester in their S1 study range. This is a valuable achievement savings for them and can be an important rising ladder in their intellectual progress during the study period and at the next level of study.